

THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH
Centre for Data, Culture & Society

CDCS ANNUAL REPORT

2019-2020

2019-2020

WE'VE BEEN BUSY.

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HELLO

WELCOME TO THE FIRST EVER ANNUAL REPORT FROM THE EDINBURGH CENTRE FOR DATA, CULTURE & SOCIETY, DRAWING TOGETHER THE RANGE OF ACTIVITIES WE'VE BEEN UP TO SINCE OUR FORMAL LAUNCH IN MAY 2019.

It's been a busy, bootstrapping year, seeing us focus on building and supporting a community of data-led researchers across the Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences at the University of Edinburgh, providing training and support for digital research methods and projects, and investing in digital infrastructures that support our work. Seeing this report laid out shows the pace and approach we've adopted: quick to respond, broad in scope, but specific in direction, with a CAHSS response to "data" running through all our activities like Blackpool rock.

There's a relatively small team behind this initiative, and I'd like to specifically thank our Centre Manager, Dr Lisa Otty, and our Centre Administrator, Cathy Naughton for all of their contributions over the past year as we have built capacity. Thanks are also due to the CAHSS Digital Innovation Team for their help in launching our online presence, in particular Ann Harrison for her brave and punchy graphic design, which is remixing and mashing up digitised content from the University of Edinburgh's collections, showing our bold and agile approach

to building this cross-college initiative. Our colleagues over at the University of Edinburgh Library and Information Services have also been a great support, including those in the Centre for Research Collections. There is a wealth of talent in digital across the University of Edinburgh, and our aim is to both surface and showcase existing activities in CAHSS, and to support new ones: the support of our colleagues across the university has helped us on our way.

At the time of writing, the Covid-19 pandemic has caused great distress and disruption across all of UK society, including universities. The digital has never been so necessary, or crucial, as it has now. It is the place of the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences to keep asking difficult questions of technology, and to provide creative and innovative interventions and provocations to the increasing digitisation of society. The report here is really a testament to what can be built, in a relatively short timeframe, when we all work towards common goals and a shared understanding of how best to support digital research in the Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences. We look forward to helping and supporting our community respond and adapt to our digital research environment, in lockdown, and beyond.

PROFESSOR MELISSA TERRAS

Director, Edinburgh Centre for Data, Culture & Society

THE CENTRE

The Edinburgh Centre for Data, Culture & Society is a hub for cross-disciplinary, data-driven and digitally-engaged research. Supporting a vibrant cross-school network of researchers within the College of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, its mission is to support, facilitate and inspire data-led and digital research within the University of Edinburgh and beyond. Together we are exploring the ways in which data and digital technology are transforming our world.

With a full programme of seminars, events and training, in our first year we have launched four new research clusters, developed an active postgraduate community, appointed new affiliates both internally and externally, and supported colleagues to host conferences and symposia.

We couldn't be prouder of everything we've achieved!

LAUNCH 2019

On the 27 March 2019, we celebrated the official launch of the Centre for Data, Culture & Society. Our founding director, Melissa Terras, introduced the centre's mission and plans and Dorothy Miell (Head of CAHSS), Jen Ross (Digital Education), and Owen Kelly (Deputy Director of the Edinburgh Futures Institute) shared their expectations and hopes for the Centre.

CDCS PEOPLE

MELISSA TERRAS
CENTRE DIRECTOR

Professor of Digital Cultural Heritage

LISA OTTY
CDCS Centre Manager

CATHY NAUGHTON
CDCS Centre Administrator

ROISIN O'BRIEN
CDCS Administrative Assistant

LEAD ACADEMICS

ARIANNA ANDREANGELI
CDCS Stakeholder Forum Chair

GALINA ANDREEVA
Business School

ANDREW CLAUSEN
School of Economics

MORGAN CURRIE
School of Social and Political Science

PETE EVANS
Moray House School of Education and Sport

MICHAEL FULLER
School of Divinity

BEVERLEY HOOD
Edinburgh College of Art

ANOUK LANG
School of Literatures, Languages and Cultures

WALID MAGDY
School of Informatics

SIOBHÁN O'CONNOR
School of Health in Social Science

XAVIER RUBIO-CAMPILLO
School of History, Classics and Archaeology

KENNY SMITH
School of Philosophy, Psychology and Language Sciences

LACHLAN URQUHART
Edinburgh Law School

BEATRICE ALEX
Edinburgh Futures Institute

PHD AFFILIATES

SUZANNE BLACK

[contemporary literature; digital fanfiction]
School of Literatures, Languages and Cultures

ELEANOR CAPALDI

[digitised art; digital engagement]
Moray House School of Education and Sport

ANNA COUTURIER

[algorithmic governance; digital health]
School of Social and Political Science

VICTORIA EVANS

[contemporary art; sonification]
Edinburgh College of Art

LUCY HAVENS

[bias in cultural heritage data; NLP]
School of Informatics

JUSTIN HO

[social network analysis; politics]
School of Social and Political Science

ASAD KHAN

[architectural design; visualisation]
Edinburgh College of Art

WENLONG LI

[advertising law; data privacy]
Edinburgh Law School

NICK MOLS

[architectural mathematics; CAD]
Edinburgh College of Art

YAZMIN MORLET CORTI

[data privacy; cybersecurity]
School of Social and Political Science

ROBYN PRITZKER

[text processing; gothic literature]
School of Literatures, Languages and Cultures

MATJAZ VIDMAR

[space exploration; earth observation]
School of Social and Political Science

RESEARCH AFFILIATES

FRANCESCA SAGGINI

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Fellow
Università degli Studi della Toscana

PHD / ECR SOCIAL EVENTS

Once a semester we host socials that give our PhD and early career researchers a chance to get together informally and meet fellow researchers with similar interests.

DATA-IN-PROGRESS SEMINAR SERIES

This year Dr Morgan Currie, a member of the CDCS core team, and Dr Juli Huang, launched Data-in-Progress: a supportive space in which postgraduate researchers can discuss their experiences of employing digital methodologies, and share any lessons learned while conducting research, or preparing for it.

Each monthly seminar features postgraduate researchers who present their research projects and details of the methods used, before opening it up to the group for general feedback and ideas.

This year's speakers were:

GREGG LLOREN

Architecture, ESALA

KEFEI WU

Accounting & Finance, Business School

SARAH BENNETT

Edinburgh College of Art / Design Informatics

VASSILIS GALANOS

STIS, School of Social and Political Sciences

91

**PHD STUDENTS
SUBSCRIBE TO OUR
OPPORTUNITIES LIST**

COVID-19: OUR RESPONSE

In March this year the whole world was severely impacted by the emergence of the novel coronavirus, Covid-19. As it became clear that travel and gatherings brought significant risk to our community, CDCS and the University of Edinburgh more broadly followed government guidance on social distancing and transitioned to remote working practices. We took a number of measures to minimise risk while trying to maximise ongoing support for our research community, cancelling seminars, using online platforms to conduct training where possible, using our digest and website to highlight remote research methods and online data and resources, and holding virtual Fikas to bring our community together.

Over the coming months, we will support our researchers as they respond to the crisis by examining the cultural and social impacts of the virus. We do not yet know when we will be able to return to our previous practices of holding face to face seminars and working together in person, but we are committed to supporting our community and maintaining continuity in our work. Our mission has always been to support and grow data-led and digital research and, as the research community pivots to work remotely and online, this mission is now more important than ever.

TRAINING

NETWORK

12

AFFILIATES

18

AFFILIATED RESEARCH CENTRES

12

SCHOOLS REPRESENTED IN OUR CORE TEAM

23

MEMBERS OF OUR STAKEHOLDER FORUM

881

EMAIL SUBSCRIBERS

SUPPORT

10

bursaries totalling
£8552 awarded
since May 2019

8

projects supported
financially

50+

people have come
along to our Fikas to
discuss their work

SEMINARS

Number of seminars

Number of attendees

WEBSITE

VISITORS

AUDIENCE

- China 1.3%
- Germany 1.4%
- Ireland 3.3%
- US 6.5%
- UK 72% (Edinburgh 30%)

Geographical breakdown of our audience

SOCIALS

395
PROFILE VIEWS

+50K
IMPRESSIONS
PER MONTH

+500
ENGAGEMENTS
PER WEEK

ADDO...

and

BLE... NES...

HON DONNE

RESEARCH

OUR RAISON D'ÊTRE.

The logo for the Centre for Data, Culture & Society (DCS) is a circular emblem. It features the letters 'DCS' in a bold, sans-serif font. The 'D' and 'C' are dark blue, while the 'S' is a vibrant pink. The letters are set against a white background within a dark blue circle.

The Centre for Data, Culture & Society was founded to support cross-disciplinary, data-driven and digital research within the College of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences.

We not only support projects, but also help to build networks and surface the expertise of our community through developing academic-led clusters that bring together researchers with shared interests. We are creating an environment in which ideas can become reality and in which connections and interchange strengthen our community and our research.

FINTECH & FINANCIAL SERVICES

Lead: Gbenga Ibikunle

New technological advancements and regulations have substantially altered how financial services are delivered. FinTech presents huge opportunities for economic and societal benefit. Innovations in FinTech can help address societal challenges such as problem debt, inequality, and climate change. But they also present new and important ethical, legal and security challenges.

We are: Creating innovative programmes focused on solving problems and applying skillsets that are relevant for the fintech workforce now and in the future; Developing interdisciplinary research to address societal challenges and explore new business models linked to the delivery of financial services; Working with partners to develop solutions to address industrial challenges for societal benefit.

RESEARCHERS

GALINA ANDREEVA
DAVID ASPINALL
BENJAMIN BACH
VAISHAK BELLE
MARIA BOUTCHKOVA
RAFFAELLA CALABRESE
YI CAO
JONATHAN CROOK
JO DANBOLT
JOHANNES DE SMEDT
YIZHE DONG
RONAN GALLAGHER
ANGELICA GONZALEZ
TIMOTHY HOSPEDALES
WENXUAN HOU
GBENGA IBIKUNLE
AGGELOS KIAYIAS
MARKULF KOHLWEISS
EWELINA LACKA
JOOSUNG LEE
BELEN MARTIN-BARRAGAN
MARIA MICHOU
FERNANDO MOREIRA
VALERIO RESTOCCHI
MICHAEL ROVATSOS
SOTIRIOS SABANIS
BEN SILA
DAVID SISKA
TAYLOR SPEARS
CHRIS SPEED
BEN SPIGEL
LUCA TASCHINI
JORDANA VIOTTO DA CRUZ
TONG WANG

RESEARCH EXPERTISE

BANKING, FINANCE AND MARKETS
ASSET PRICING AND INVESTMENT
MANAGEMENT SCIENCE AND
OPERATIONS RESEARCH
MACHINE LEARNING AND
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
DESIGN INFORMATICS AND DATA
SCIENCE
TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION,
E-COMMERCE, BLOCKCHAIN
ECONOMIC SOCIOLOGY /
PHILOSOPHY
CYBERSECURITY
ETHICS OF TECHNOLOGY USE

EVENTS

ECONOMICS OF FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGY CONFERENCE

17th - 19th June 2020 (now postponed)

The Edinburgh Futures Institute and the University of Edinburgh Business School are organising the First Edinburgh Conference on the Economics of Financial Technology in order to stimulate debate and research on financial innovation and the digital economy and how they impact welfare. The conference aims to bring together academics, policymakers, and finance professionals to share new insights and discuss the economic issues related to the application of technology to the practice of finance in a rapidly evolving regulatory landscape.

RESEARCH SEMINAR SERIES

In this research seminars series, leading researchers from across the University of Edinburgh and partner research institutions will offer an unvarnished view of the emerging sector at the intersection of finance, technology and policy. They will advance debates on topical issues in FinTech and its interaction with society, from technological innovations to regulatory issues.

BUSINESS SCHOOL

SCHOOL OF MATHEMATICS

This graph represents the distribution of FinTech cluster membership and expertise across the College of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences. Each dot represents a researcher.

EDINBURGH COLLEGE OF ART

INFORMATICS

- Banking, Finance and Markets
- Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence
- Economic Sociology/Philosophy
- Asset Pricing and Investment
- Design Informatics and Data Science
- Cybersecurity and Ethics of Technology Use
- Management Science and Operations Research
- Technology and Innovation, E-commerce, Blockchain

MEDIA & COMMUNICATIONS

Lead: Kate Wright

We investigate the rapidly changing role of data in communication, as well as digital media more broadly. We take a unique, interdisciplinary approach to this work, bringing together media experts from across the College and beyond. Some of our members take media and communications as their object of study, whilst others engage in research as a form of media practice.

Our outlook is global. We study Scottish and British media, as well as media in Africa, East and South Asia, Latin America, the Middle East and the Pacific. We are all profoundly interested in meaning-making, trust and the exercise of power.

RESEARCHERS

BENJAMIN BACH
TOM BOYLSTON
CHRIS CARTER
PAULO CAVALIERE
ANDREW CONNOR
RICHARD COYNE
LAURA CRAM
RACHAEL CRAUFURD SMITH
JULIE CUPPLES
CORENTIN CURCHOD
MORGAN CURRIE
EMMA DAVIE
MAGGIE DWYER
OLIVER ESCOBAR
JEAN-BENOIT FALISSE
CHARLOTTE GLEGHORN
KAREN GREGORY
ROBIN HILL
LOTTE HOEK
EMMA HUNTER
ITANDEHUI JANSEN
BRONWYN JONES
GEORGE KAREKWAIVANANE
SMITA KHERIA
ERIC LAURIER
JOHN LEE
SARAH LIU
CLARE LLEWELLYN
EWA LUGER

WALID MAGDY
EBTIHAL MAHADEEN
ISMAY MILFORD
JOLYON MITCHELL
THOMAS MOLONY
JONNY MURRAY
DAVE O'BRIEN
KATE ORTON-JOHNSON
CLAUDIA PAGLIARI
CHRIS PERKINS
NICK PRIOR
JULES RAWLINSON
RAQUEL RIBEIRO
MERLIN SELLER
DAVID SORFA
CHRIS SPEED
KATE SYMONS
MARIA WOLTERS
KATE WRIGHT

RESEARCH EXPERTISE

JOURNALISM
SOCIAL MEDIA
SCREEN STUDIES
DIGITAL DESIGN
DATA
POLITICAL COMMUNICATIONS

EVENTS

AFTER THE CRISIS: REIMAGINING JOURNALISM AND PUBLIC MEDIA

Victor Pickard
University of Pennsylvania
31 January 2020

This graph represents the distribution of Media & Communications cluster membership and expertise across the College of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences.

Each collection of connected dots represents a researcher.

DIGITAL CULTURAL HERITAGE

Lead: Jen Ross

The Digital Cultural Heritage cluster brings together researchers from

across the University of Edinburgh who work on analysing, understanding and developing new approaches to the relationships between data, digital and cultural heritage.

Working with a wide range of partners in the gallery, library, archive and museum sectors, cluster members are researching tangible and intangible cultural heritage as it relates to digital preservation, sharing and copyright, new audiences, organisational transformation, learning from collections, community engagement, tourism, curatorial practice, text mining, and geographical information systems.

Our research spans both local and global heritage contexts, and draws on a wide range of theoretical perspectives.

DIGITAL SOCIAL SCIENCE

Leads: Morgan Currie, Karen Gregory, Kate Miltner

The Digital Social Science Cluster focuses on teaching and research in the digital social sciences. Hosting a series of events, the cluster looks at the affordances and limitations of

new digital methods, research ethics, data access issues, problems related to corporate relationships, and the design and use of new tools. As a “methods lab”, Digital Social Science makes methods, tools, datasets, and projects accessible to students and staff.

RESEARCH EXPERTISE

**COPYRIGHT
INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY
ACCESS
DIGITAL DOCUMENTATION
DIGITAL ENGAGEMENT, LEARNING
AND PARTICIPATION
GEOSPATIAL DATA AND HERITAGE
TOURISM AND HERITAGE
WORKING WITH DIGITAL ARCHIVES
AND COLLECTIONS**

RESEARCH EXPERTISE

In the wake of the Covid-19 pandemic this cluster has brought forward its website to share examples of digital methods as researchers adapt to remote data gathering and analysis.

EVENTS

RESPONSIBLE OPERATIONS: PREVIEWING A COMMUNITY RESEARCH AGENDA

Thomas Padilla | OCLC Research
29 October 2019

MUSEUMS AND AI: IMAGINING THE AI WE WANT FOR MUSEUMS

Oonagh Murphy | Goldsmiths, University
of London
June 2020 (Date TBC)

EVENTS

Digital Social Science will launch a programme of methods-led events in 2020/21

PROJECTS

WE'RE ON A DATA MISSION

A key part of our mission is to support our community as they work on new ideas and pilot projects. Every year we will run a call for experimental and innovative projects focused on data and computational methods, so as to help get ideas off the ground and sow the seeds of bigger plans. In 2019, we asked our community to propose small technical development projects that we could assist with: the resulting projects ranged from the medical humanities in Malawi, through digital manuscripts in England, to the history of slavery in Jamaican archives, and gives a real flavour of the kinds of exciting work being conducted within CAHSS. We hope this year's call, focused on text-mining, will prove even more fruitful.

MALAWIAN (HI) STORIES AND THE MEDICAL HUMANITIES

Dr Chisomo Kalinga aims to provide the first multidisciplinary archive on medical humanities in Malawi as part of her Wellcome Trust funded project 'Ulimbaso "You will be strong again": How literary aesthetics and storytelling inform concepts of health and wellbeing in Malawi'. The digital archive has been upgraded, enabling the site to be converted from a personal archive to an international open source data platform. It will provide a historical and modern resource for researchers, academics, health professionals, archivists, and others, with the capacity to inform policy and research in Scotland, Malawi, and on an international scale.

ENCODING THE VANDEGRIFTER

A collection of unpublished short stories by the American writer Fanny Van de Grift Stevenson was recently discovered in her archives.

As the wife of Robert Louis Stevenson, Fanny Stevenson's own literary work has been largely overlooked by scholars to date. Dr Robyn Pritzker undertook the digitisation of these stories in collaboration with Dr Anouk Lang, in order to make the stories available to the public for the first time. The completed digital edition demonstrates the potential for using TEI markup to illuminate the previously overlooked importance of Stevenson's work.

SOFTWARE AS A RESEARCH TOOL

Led by Dr Nataša Pantić, this project aims to develop a software that functions both as a tool for research and research-informed professional development of teachers and other education professionals. It builds on a pilot project to improve the functionality of the online log for Teacher Reflection on their Agency for Change (TRAC) to enable taking to scale empirical study of the impact of teachers' social networks. It will enable researchers and teachers anywhere to engage with the web-based log and receive feedback about their work and their own networks.

JAMAICA MANUMISSIONS PROJECT

Professor Diana Paton has undertaken the Jamaica Manumissions Project, a study of deed book records held in the Jamaica Archives which detail the manumission (release from slavery) of hundreds of people in Jamaica between the 1740s and the 1830s. CDCS funded the development of an online database to facilitate collection of the data in volumes that have already been digitised, which has enabled improved database efficiency and automation processes for further data collection.

A DIGITAL EDITION OF ALICE THORNTON'S BOOKS

Dr Cordelia Beattie and Dr Suzanne Trill have created a prototype website for a digital edition of four autobiographical manuscripts by Alice Thornton, a seventeenth-century writer, that have important implications for our understanding of the author and the composition of such materials in this period.

The project aims to produce an online edition in which each text could be read continuously, while also being searchable via an index and keywords.

CDCS TEXT MINING LAB

THE CENTRE FOR DATA, CULTURE & SOCIETY IS SEEKING HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCE RESEARCHERS WHO CAN ASK COMPLEX QUESTIONS OF LARGE-SCALE DATA SETS.

This is an exciting opportunity for researchers to explore new dimensions of textual data sets including over 68,000 British Library books and newspapers, the Times Digital Archive and the Encyclopaedia Britannica.

We have created **DEFOE**, a new text and data mining facility at the University of Edinburgh for interrogating large text-based archives, and welcome help to explore how we might develop the system further.

Researchers don't need to have programming skills - we have an EPCC programmer on board who will help - they need only the use of subject expertise to pose interesting questions and explore the data.

DATASETS

BRITISH LIBRARY BOOKS

Over 68,000 books from the 16th to the 19th century, covering geography, philosophy, history, poetry and literature in a variety of languages.

BRITISH LIBRARY NEWSPAPERS

1TB of digitised British newspapers from the 18th to the early 20th century.

PAPERS PAST: NEW ZEALAND AND PACIFIC NEWSPAPERS

Over 5 million pages of New Zealand and Pacific newspapers from the 19th and 20th centuries.

TIMES DIGITAL ARCHIVE

All the articles in 69,699 volumes of The Times newspaper between 1785 and 2009.

GAZETTEERS OF SCOTLAND

20 volumes of the most popular 19th Century gazetteers of Scotland, including detailed historical and geographic information about each place.

ENCYCLOPAEDIA BRITANNICA 1768 - 1860

The first 8 volumes of the Encyclopaedia Britannica, issued from 1768-1860, comprising a total of 143 volumes. 155,388 pages, 166m words.

COMING SOON

JISC MEDICAL HERITAGE LIBRARY

HANSARD ARCHIVE

STATISTICAL ACCOUNTS OF SCOTLAND

DIGITISED THESES FROM EDINBURGH UNIVERSITY LIBRARY

“ FUNDING FROM THE CDCS WAS INVALUABLE IN ENABLING THE DEVELOPMENT OF ‘WE BEGAN AS PART OF THE BODY’, MY PRACTICE BASED RESEARCH PROJECT, WORKING ACROSS THE FIELDS OF ART, SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY. ”

BEVERLEY HOOD

TRAINING

BUILDING

DATA

SKILLS.

**EXCELLENT OVERVIEW,
AND IT WAS USEFUL TO
CONSOLIDATE TRAINING
FROM OTHER QGIS/ARCGIS
TRAINING WORKSHOPS.**

JUSTIN HO

Training fellow

Justin Ho is a PhD researcher based in the School of Social and Political Science. His research focuses on the rise of nationalism in Hong Kong as communicated via social media, namely Facebook. Justin's research employs a range of digital methods, including computational text analysis and social network analysis.

LUCIA MICHELIN

Training fellow

Lucia Michielin earned a PhD in Classics from the University of Edinburgh in 2019. Her work to date has focused on utilising GIS, databases, and 3D reconstructions for classics and archaeological research. Lucia specialises in the field of Digital Humanities and has been involved with numerous UK-based and European research projects.

Our training programmes draw on expertise across the University of Edinburgh, ranging from workshops led by professional colleagues in Information Services to skills sharing sessions led by PhD students.

We have introduced a 'peer cohort' stream of training, led by our two CDCS training fellows, which makes use of existing online materials and MOOC courses and brings together small groups to study and work together. In spring this year we also brought in external trainers to supplement our remote training offering.

“ **VERY CLEAR, PATIENT PRESENTER. HELPFUL SCRIPTS THAT I CAN USE LATER.** ”

COURSES

CODE DOJO: PYTHON

AN INTRODUCTION TO DATABASES USING SQLITE

AN INTRODUCTION TO TEXT ANALYSIS

INTRODUCTION TO SPATIAL DATA AND GIS

INTRODUCTION TO TEXT ENCODING WITH TEI

PAINLESS INTRODUCTION TO R

VISUALIZING YOUR DATA USING R

WEB SCRAPING NEWS SITES WITH PYTHON

WORKING WITH HISTORICAL MAPS IN DIGIMAP

INTERMEDIATE TEXT ANALYSIS

DATA-IN-PROGRESS METHODS SERIES (FOR PHD STUDENTS & POSTGRADS)

PUTTING SPATIAL DATA ONLINE USING MAPBOX

VISUALISING SPATIAL DATA IN QGIS

WEBSCRAPING NEWS SITES WITH PYTHON

LIBRARY CARPENTRY

INTRODUCTION TO WORKING WITH DATA (REGULAR EXPRESSIONS)

OPENREFINE

TIDY DATA FOR LIBRARIANS

PROGRAMMING HISTORIAN

DO YOU NEED TO LEARN PROGRAMMING? A SELF-CRITIQUE

THE PROGRAMMING HISTORIAN SILENT DISCO

DOCUMENTING YOUR DIGITAL METHODS

DATA CARPENTRY

DATA CARPENTRY FOR SOCIAL SCIENTISTS - SPREADSHEETS/ OPENREFINE

DATA CARPENTRY FOR SOCIAL SCIENTISTS - INTRO TO R

DATA CARPENTRY FOR SOCIAL SCIENTISTS - R FOR ANALYSIS & VISUALISATION

DATA CARPENTRY FOR SOCIAL SCIENTISTS - DATA MANAGEMENT WITH SQL

PEER LEARNING COHORTS

INTRODUCTION TO MARKDOWN

RELATIONAL DATABASES AND SQL

VERSION CONTROL AND COLLABORATIVE DOCUMENTS WITH GIT

WRITE AND FORMAT YOUR THESIS WITH LATEX AND OVERLEAF

PYTHON FOR EVERYBODY (AUTUMN 2019)

PYTHON FOR EVERYBODY (SPRING 2020)

STATISTICS AND VISUALISATION WITH R

WORKSHOPS

AN INTRODUCTION TO LIDAR TECHNOLOGY

DISCOVER THE LIBRARY'S DIGITAL PRIMARY SOURCE COLLECTIONS

COLLECTING AND ANALYSING TWITTER NETWORKS IN R

**GOOD INTRODUCTION,
MADE IT LESS INTIMIDATING
TO EXPLORE PROGRAMMING
IN GENERAL.**

SEMINARS

With speakers from across the UK and beyond, our cross-disciplinary weekly seminar programme has featured something for everyone.

THE WICKED FINDINGS OF THE WITCHFINDER GENERAL: PUTTING ACCUSED WITCHES ON THE MAP

Emma Carroll; Ewan McAndrew

University of Edinburgh

ENCODING THE VANDEGRIFTER: A DIGITAL EDITION OF FANNY VAN DE GRIFT STEVENSON'S UNPUBLISHED STORIES

Robyn Pritzker; Anouk Lang

University of Edinburgh

SUSTAINABLE FASHION: CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY IN SUPPLY CHAINS

Patsy Perry

University of Manchester

CAN VIRTUAL AGENTS LEARN HOW TO HAVE A CONVERSATION?

Verena Rieser

Heriot-Watt University

RESPONSIBLE OPERATIONS: PREVIEWING A COMMUNITY RESEARCH AGENDA

Thomas Padilla

OCLC Research

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS AN ARTISTIC MEDIUM

Colin Johnson

University of Kent; IASH

CULTURAL MAPPING: CROSS-DISCIPLINARY APPROACHES

Vikki Jones; Liz McFall; Candace Jones; Inge Panneels; Morgan Currie

University of Edinburgh; Napier University

DIGITAL CULTURAL HERITAGE: EMOTIONAL ENGAGEMENT, STORYTELLING & CO-CREATION

Maria Economou

University of Glasgow

LEARNING HOW TO FAIL BETTER: RESILIENCE IN DIGITAL HUMANITIES PROJECTS

James Cummings

Newcastle University

THE INVISIBLE EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA

Ben Marder

University of Edinburgh

HANSARD DEBATES THROUGH A TELESCOPE: DIGITAL PARLIAMENTARY RECORDS

Marc Alexander

University of Glasgow

MAPPING RELIGIOUS CHANGE WITH MESSY DATA: THE SCOTTISH REFORMATION, 1560 - 1689

Mikki Brock; Chris Langley

Washington and Lee University; Newman University Birmingham

SONGS AT THE INTERFACE: COMMUNITY INTERACTIONS WITH ONLINE COLLECTIONS

Linda Barwick

University of Sydney

CURATORIAL LABOUR, VOICE, & LEGACY: MARY DOROTHY GEORGE'S CATALOGUES

James Baker

University of Sussex

AFTER THE CRISIS: REIMAGINING JOURNALISM AND PUBLIC MEDIA

Victor Pickard

University of Pennsylvania

“**SPEAKERS AND PRESENTATION WERE EXCELLENT AND TOPIC WAS FASCINATING. EXCELLENT SEMINAR AND AN EXCELLENT EXAMPLE OF A TRANSDISCIPLINARY TOPIC.**”

**LITERARY TRANSLATORS ON
TECHNOLOGY: NAVIGATING A NEW
PROFESSIONAL LANDSCAPE**

Paola Ruffo

Heriot-Watt University

**ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AS AN
ARTISTIC MEDIUM**

Colin Johnson

University of Kent; IASH

**RADICAL PROTOCOLS: DESIGNING
DEMOCRATIC DIGITAL TOOLS IN
SOCIAL MOVEMENTS**

Jessica Feldman

American University of Paris

**DEMONS, DILDOS & DANCING
SKELETONS: MACHINE LEARNING AT
WELLCOME COLLECTION**

Harrison Pim

Wellcome Collection

**MUSEUMS AND AI: IMAGINING THE AI
WE WANT FOR MUSEUMS**

Oonagh Murphy

Goldsmiths, University of London

**WELCOMING,
SUPPORTIVE AND
HUGELY MOTIVATING.**

COLLABORATION

IASH FELLOWSHIPS

INSTITUTE FOR ADVANCED STUDIES IN THE HUMANITIES

We partner with IASH to offer funded Digital Scholarship Visiting Fellowships and Digital Scholarship Postdoctoral Fellowships each year.

VISITING RESEARCH FELLOWS 2019–2020

MIKKI BROCK (WASHINGTON AND LEE UNIVERSITY, VIRGINIA)

Mikki Brock's fellowship project is titled 'Mapping the Scottish Reformation', a database and mapping investigation exploring the lives, movements, and networks of the Scottish clergy between 1560 and 1689. Her research interests centre on religious belief and identity in early modern Scotland.

COLIN JOHNSON (UNIVERSITY OF KENT)

During his fellowship, Colin Johnson worked on a project analysing the use of AI in the visual arts. Colin's research interests centre on artificial intelligence and creative intelligence, and his work focuses on improving AI algorithms and the kinds of problems that AI can tackle, the use of AI in music, mathematics, engineering, bioinformatics, and the digital humanities.

POSTDOCTORAL FELLOW: ALICE KELLY

Alice Kelly identified overlapping resonances with Joseph Conrad's characters in contemporary popular film during her PhD, which started off her interest in studying fan fiction and queer literature of the digital age. Alice's postdoctoral research positions femslash (female-female) fan fiction within the history of lesbian literary adaptation.

PARTNERS

READ-COOP

The University of Edinburgh is a founding partner in the new READ-COOP which oversees the development of the Transkribus platform. Melissa Terras is on the Board of Directors of READ-COOP.

NATIONAL LIBRARY OF SCOTLAND

In partnership with the Digital Scholarship Service, we support the use of the Library's Data Foundry and work together on training initiatives. We also collaborate with the Library on projects on a regular basis, most recently on a creative project to 3-D scan and then render parts of the library building hidden under their public reading rooms on George IV Bridge.

IMPROVERTS & EDINBURGH FESTIVALS

Melissa Terras is working with Improverts, the University of Edinburgh student improvisation troupe, and the Edinburgh Festivals, to look at how Artificial Intelligence can support - or disrupt- ideas to build improvisation around, and help us identify previous trends and tropes in the performing arts. In a (now) digital only project for the 2020 Festival season, they'll be working together to remix and remash the last eight years of festival programming, experimenting with previous show data, to provide the world's first bot-generated arts festival.

UCREATE STUDIO

CDCS works with the UCreate Studio to provide new technology for our research community, and to make the datasets produced by our community available through the University's Datashare service.

CENTRE FOR RESEARCH COLLECTIONS

We use the Digital Scholarship Centre and collections data provided by the Centre for Research Collections in the University Library.

EVENTS

ILLICIT ANTIQUITIES TRADE ON SOCIAL MEDIA WORKSHOP

This workshop brought together archaeologists, criminologists and representatives of law enforcement to discuss the social context of antiquity trafficking, the tools used for finding and analysing trafficking data effectively, and the various methods used to keep pace with the ever-changing platforms commonly used. Presenters and delegates attended from institutions in the UK, the Netherlands, Germany, Latvia, Sweden, Italy, and the USA.

RE-ANIMATING DATA WORKSHOP

This one-day workshop launched a digital archive of qualitative interviews created using Omeka, a free open source content management system for small (and not so small) qualitative projects. Participants learned about archiving qualitative research datasets and making them available for re-use, as well as uses for teaching, further research and for developing and engaging with user communities.

INVESTMENT

MONEY

WELL

SPENT.

The Centre for Data, Culture & Society is financed by the College of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences at the University of Edinburgh. We spend the majority of our budget on staff, training and research events and projects. We use what remains to support research by responding to the needs of our community.

EQUIPMENT

Over the last 12 months, CDCS has supported the purchase of circa £30,000 worth of hardware and software to enable our researchers to conduct their cutting edge work.

This has included a wide range of equipment, including a ceramics 3D printer, VR headsets and LiDAR scanners.

DEFOE

CDCS is partnering with colleagues at EPCC to support the development of a new text and data mining facility at the University of Edinburgh called **defoe**.

Using the power of analytic frameworks, such as Apache Spark, Jupyter Notebooks, and High Performing Computing environments, it allows researchers to manipulate and mine huge digitised archives in parallel at great speed using a simple command line. We are seed-funding projects and facilitating playful experiments to learn about what **defoe** can do and the directions in which it might develop.

TEI BY EXAMPLE

TEI By Example is a well-used web resource offering freely available online tutorials that assist researchers learning the guidelines of the Text Encoding Initiative. The tutorials provide a general introduction to text encoding, and example-based introductions to different aspects of electronic text markup for the humanities. This year CDCS is funding a complete content refresh of the resource for the academic community, which will be released in the summer of 2020.

35,000+

GBP OF INVESTMENT IN DIGITAL HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE IN 2019

BURSARIES

OWEN G. PARRY IASH

ROBYN PRITZKER LLC

LUIS REYES Law

KATH BASSETT SPS

ADAM FERRON LLC

BRIDGET MOYNIHAN LLC

ANOUK LANG LLC

REBECCA COLLINS ECA

JAMES BESSE SPS

VIKKI JONES ECA

SaaS-Fee Summer Institute of Art 2019

New York City, US (June 2019)

Digital Humanities Summer Institute

University of Victoria, Canada (June 2019)

Data Analysis and Design of Experiments with R Workshop

University of Barcelona, Spain (July 2019)

Digital Methods Summer School

Amsterdam, Netherlands (July 2019)

DH2019 'Culture Analytics' Workshop

Utrecht, Netherlands (July 2019)

PICA 'On Val Del Omar' Workshop

Azala, La Sierra, Spain (November 2019)

Digital Methods Winter School & Data Sprint

Amsterdam, Netherlands (January 2020)

BUDGET 2019/2020 BREAKDOWN

TOTAL SPEND £165K

2021-2022

WE'VE GOT PLANS.

Next year our focus will be on:

GROWING OUR TEAM

**DEVELOPING OUR COMMUNITY EXPERTISE IN
TEXT MINING AND TEXT ANALYSIS**

REFINING OUR TRAINING OFFERING

**CONTINUING TO PROVIDE ALL THE SUPPORT
WE CAN TO OUR COMMUNITY!**

THE UNIVERSITY *of* EDINBURGH
Centre for Data, Culture & Society

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